

1 **Xist activity in HPV+ and HPV- cancer of the head and neck.**

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7 We discovered and described activation of Xist, the non-coding RNA that silences duplicate X
8 chromosomes in females to execute dosage compensation in transformation of solid tissues using
9 p53-sufficient and p53-deficient cancer cells. We next found that Xist activation was an authentic
10 transcriptional consequence of mutation or loss of the tumor suppressors p53 or Rb. We quantified and
11 characterized Xist activation in humans with breast cancer and humans with non-small cell lung cancer.
12 Xist promoted transcriptional heterogeneity during transformation and instructed subtype selection. We
13 have described and are describing the existence and composition of putative Xist RNP complexes that
14 function to enhance clonal fitness by repression or activation of genes using the epigenetic modularity and
15 capacity of Xist.

16 We report here significant transcriptional modulation of Xist in humans with head and neck cancer.
17 Mobilization of Xist in transformation of the head and neck was found in both men and women and
18 appeared independent of tissue type (tongue, tonsil, uvula, palate, etc.). In one cohort, we found Xist
19 among the most transcriptionally active and differentially expressed genes transcriptome-wide in HPV
20 negative (-) head and neck cancer, but not in HPV+ head and neck cancer. Silencing or activation of Xist
21 during transformation is a fundamental transcriptional quality of transformation in solid tumors in man and
22 it is driven by loss of tumor suppressor (p53/Rb) function.
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Results

Figure 1: Xist is active in head and neck cancer in humans.

I. GSE56142

n=12 control

n=12 tumor

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
ILMN_176457	6.31e-01	0.4870298	-5.957225	2.59e-01	XIST	20100/27445	26.8

In this dataset, the change in Xist expression between normal tissue and tumor tissue was minimal, and the minimal change was decreased in nature.

II. GSE83519

n=22 control

n=22 tumor

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
9387	4.30e-04	3.8013227	-0.649245	0.4558667	XIST	9384/43179	78.3

In this dataset, the change in Xist expression between normal tissue and tumor tissue was significant, but the change was still decreased in nature.

Thus, our state-of-the-art methods which identify differentially expressed genes by ranking magnitude of difference in expression of all transcripts measured transcriptome-wide calculated Xist differential expression as either marginal or significant, but in each case repressive (down-regulated) in nature. Unfortunately, these datasets were heterogeneous in composition, in what is already a heterogeneous disease, varying based on etiology (HPV status) and tissue type (arising from multiple tissue types of the oral cavity).

Figure 2: Xist expression in head and neck cancer varies based on HPV status.

GSE211322: HPV negative head and neck cancers.

n=2 normal tissues of the head and neck (control)

n=4 HPV- head and neck cancer (primary tumor; human)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
7503	NA	3.974	-2.2858339	-9.0842494	2339.64	XIST	19081/19126	0.2

GSE211322: HPV positive head and neck cancers.

n=2 normal tissues of the head and neck (control)

n=4 HPV+ head and neck cancer (primary tumor; human)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
7503	1.67e-03	2.638	-3.1434501	-8.2909067	1286.86	XIST	285/19126	98.5

1 Thus, Xist is indeed actively transcribed and expressed in head and neck cancer; in this dataset, Xist was
2 among the genes whose expression was most significantly different transcriptome-wide when comparing
3 HPV- head and neck cancers. Xist transcript production in HPV+ head and neck cancers was almost
4 undetectable.

5 **Figure 3: Xist expression in head and neck cancer varies based on patient sex.**

6 GSE117973

7 *n*=60 primary tumors from men with head and neck cancer
8 *n*=17 primary tumors from women with head and neck cancer

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
ILMN_1764573	1.95e-18	-1.15e+01	22.26015	-2.19124777	XIST	2/47323	99.996

10 GSE163173

11 *n*=216 primary tumors from men with head and neck cancer
12 *n*=70 primary tumors from women with head and neck cancer

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
TC0X00010060.hg.1	1.74e-55	-19.7364779	73.84153	-3.87840608	XIST	1/35750	99.997

14 **Discussion**

15 We described here expression and expression patterns of the non-coding RNA Xist in cancer of the head
16 and neck in humans. Xist expression changes in the head and tumor varied from cohort to cohort, but
17 some patterns in change were noticeable: Xist expression was high in the female tumor and Xist
18 expression was high in head and neck cancers that were HPV negative. Xist expression in human head
19 and neck cancer is heterogenous and varies based on HPV status and patient sex.
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